

Motivation amongst Library Professionals is the need of hour for the Management of Libraries: a Study

Manisha Gupta¹, Harpreet Kaur², Preeti Sharda³

Abstract

Our guiding Source Shiyali Ramamrita Ranganathan (1892-1972), the father of Library Science in India propounded the Five Laws of Library Science which are still very much relevant in this digital Era. The user satisfaction and optimum utilization of the library resources are the crux points of his philosophy. To achieve the optimum user satisfaction and utilization of information resources, the Library Professionals play the most important role. In this Digital era when the libraries are changing due to the impact of ICT, globalization and changing user needs, the Library Professionals are also facing a great change and lots of expectations from the users. The Library organizations need to motivate the Library Professionals in various ways for the efficient and effective working of the Libraries. In this paper, various theories of motivation have been examined and some ways and techniques have been suggested to motivate the Library Professionals for the most efficient and effective working of the Libraries. Further a study was conducted to find out the level of work motivation among the librarians working in the colleges of Chandigarh.

Key Words

Job satisfaction, Librarians, Personnel Management, Management of Libraries, Motivation, Motivation Theories

1. Manisha Gupta, Librarian, Govt. College of Art, Sector 10-C, Chandigarh E-Mail: guptacga10@gmail.com

2. Harpreet Kaur, Library assistant, Panjab University, Chandigarh E-Mail: harpreet_cancer@yahoo.co.in

3. Preeti Sharda, Librarian, RIE, Sector 32, Chandigarh. E-mail: sharda.preeti@gmail.com